

Pedagogical Endeavor As Mediator on Engagement-Based Teaching Approach and Basic Life Skills of Senior High School Students

Gina S. Hinlo

Abstract. The main purpose of this study was to evaluate whether pedagogical endeavor have significant mediating effect on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students. In this study, the researcher selected the 200 senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City as the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected on the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson-r Correlation, and Baron and Kenny's (1986) Method for Mediation with Sobel z-Test. Descriptive analysis showed that engagement-based teaching approach, basic life skills of senior high school students, pedagogical endeavor in Tagum South District in Tagum City were described as extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is significant relationship among engagement-based teaching approach, basic life skills of senior high school students, and pedagogical endeavor. Evidently, Baron and Kenny's (1986) Method for Mediation through regression analysis and Sobel z-test proved that pedagogical endeavor have significant mediating effect on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students. The study, therefore, was conducted for further utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management
2. engagement-based teaching approach
3. pedagogical endeavor

Date Received: May 21, 2024 — Date Reviewed: May 23, 2024 — Date Published: June 5, 2024

1. Introduction

The importance of an engagement-based teaching approach, the development of basic life skills in students, and pedagogical endeavor on educational processes is multifaceted and interconnected, as each element contributes significantly to the overall quality of education and students' holistic development. Engagement-based teaching encourages active participation, critical thinking, and problem-solving among students.

It shifts the focus from passive reception of information to active engagement with the material, resulting in better understanding and retention. The importance of an engagement-based teaching approach, the development of basic life skills in students, and pedagogical endeavor in educational processes cannot be overstated. Together, these elements create a dynamic and effective learning environment that equips stu-

dents with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes they need to succeed academically, personally, and professionally in an ever-changing world. Therefore, analyzing the role of pedagogical endeavor as mediator can play an important role in understanding the influence of engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of the students. Kashlev (2013) pointed out that engagement-based teaching approach can significantly improve basic life skills in students by offering a dynamic and engaging learning experience that fosters practical application, critical thinking, and social development. Accordingly, engagement-based teaching approach encourages active participation and engagement from students. Instead of passively listening to lectures or reading from textbooks, students are actively involved in the learning process, which promotes better understanding and retention of the skills being taught. Adding more, Cetin-Dindar (2016) pointed out that engagement-based teaching approach promotes collaboration and teamwork, where students work together to achieve common goals. This cultivates their ability to work effectively in groups, appreciate diverse perspectives, and resolve conflicts constructively. As highlighted by Pérez-Guilarte et al. (2022), pedagogical endeavor is the process of learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in teaching practice. According to Tanang and Abu (2014) high-level pedagogical endeavor involves tailoring instruction to individual students' learning styles, abilities, and interests, fostering more effective and personalized learning. Govranos and Newton (2014) also pointed out that high-level pedagogical endeavor cultivates a culture of lifelong learning and continuous improvement among educators. Adding more, Goudreau et al. (2015) concluded that teachers who demonstrate a strong commitment to pedagogical endeavor often become leaders in their schools, guiding

and inspiring their colleagues. As described by Reeves (2012), engagement-based teaching approach is the pedagogical strategy in education that focuses on actively involving students in the learning process by promoting their participation, interaction, and interest in the subject matter. According to Reutova (2015), this approach goes beyond traditional didactic teaching methods and emphasizes creating an engaging and interactive classroom environment where students are motivated to explore, discuss, and apply their knowledge. In addition, Kutbiddinova (2015) asserted that interactive activities teach students patience, tolerance, and understanding towards others and encourage them to think outside the box. As noted by Kutbiddinova et al. (2016), engagement-based teaching actively involves students in the learning process, leading to deeper understanding and improved retention of the material. When students are engaged, they are more likely to master complex concepts and skills. Erawan (2010) described basic life skills as the abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. According to Naseri and Babakhani (2016), life skills assist people to be adaptable, interact with the environment, and promote self-management. Also, Greco, Baer, and Smith (2013) asserted that basic life skills include life skills, effective communication skills, interpersonal relationships, empathy, decision-making, problem-solving, critical thinking, and self-awareness, as well as the capacity to control emotions like stress, anxiety, depression, and failure. It help individuals to control such problems as depression, anxiety, loneliness, rejection, anger, and conflict in social relationships. In contrary, poor basic life skills among students can have significant consequences that affect various aspects of their lives, both in the short term and the long term. The report of Naseri and Babakhani (2016) showed that inadequate problem-solving skills may hinder

students' ability to navigate complex academic tasks and challenges. According to Kawalekar (2017), poor basic life skills, such as time management and organization, can lead to academic struggles. Students may have difficulty managing their study time effectively, meeting deadlines, and staying focused on their studies, resulting in lower academic performance. Similarly, Pitan (2013) pointed out that students with poor life skills may resort to unhealthy coping mechanisms, such as substance abuse, excessive screen time, or disengagement from responsibilities, as a way to manage stress and difficulties. Talking things in Philippine setting, Tindowen et al. (2015) reported that students who struggle with basic life skills may experience lower self-esteem and self-confidence, impacting their overall well-being and sense of self-worth. Despite the growing body of literature on engagement-based teaching approaches and their positive impact on student outcomes, there is a noticeable research gap concerning

the mediating effect of pedagogical endeavor on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approaches and the development of basic life skills among students. While existing research has explored the direct association between engagement-based teaching and life skills, there is a dearth of studies that systematically investigate the role of teachers' pedagogical efforts as a mediating variable in this relationship. Thus, it is on this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Tagum South District, Tagum City using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made used descriptive correlational design by means of mediation analysis. This approach provides insights into the mechanisms, processes, or mediators that explain why an independent variable influences a dependent variable. This knowledge helps build a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized quantitative descriptive-correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts and information related to the engagement-based teaching approach, pedagogical endeavor, and basic life skills of senior high school students. Bryman and Bell (2015) described quantitative research as a research method that focuses on the objective measurement and analysis of numerical data to draw conclusions and make inferences about a specific population or phenomenon. This approach employs systematic and structured data collection techniques, such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis of existing datasets, to gather numerical data that can be quantified and

statistically analyzed. The findings from quantitative research aim to provide a deeper understanding of patterns, relationships, and trends within the data. Meanwhile, mediation analysis is a statistical method used to quantify the causal sequence by which an antecedent variable causes a mediating variable that causes a dependent variable (Mackinnon, 2019). Specifically, the study focused on determining the mediating effect of pedagogical endeavor on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students. In mediation analysis defines the direct, indirect, and total effects in terms of the linear regression coefficients. The total effect is defined and estimated as the *c* coefficient

and the direct effect is defined and estimated as the *c'* coefficient. The indirect effect is defined and estimated as the product of the *a* and *b* coefficients (*ab*) and as the difference between the *c* coefficient and the *c'* coefficient. In this study, the researcher made use of mediation analysis because it provides information about the process by which an independent variable affects a dependent variable.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. In this study, the 200 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those bonafied enrolled senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City, those who do not have back subjects or failing grades, and those who vol-

untarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the socio-economic status of senior high school students.

2.3. Research Instrument—Two sets of instruments were used in this study. These questionnaires were subjected for content validity by panel of experts and undergone pilot testing to test its validity and reliability. The comments, corrections, and suggestions given by the experts were incorporated in the final revisions of the questionnaires. The first part of the instrument concerned about the engagement-based teaching approach which consists of three domains namely: teaching engagement, interaction, and feedback. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Chronbach's alpha value of 0.950. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of engagement-based teaching approach, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below.

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The engagement-based teaching approach is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The engagement-based teaching approach is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The engagement-based teaching approach is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The engagement-based teaching approach is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The engagement-based teaching approach is never observed.

The second tool is about the basic life skills of the students. This questionnaire was divided into indicators namely: critical thinking, creative thinking, self-awareness, interpersonal relationship and communication skills, and decision making and problem solving skills. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall

Chronbach’s alpha value of 0.940. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of basic life skills of the students, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below.

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The basic life skills of senior high school students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The basic life skills of senior high school students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The basic life skills of senior high school students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The basic life skills of senior high school students is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The basic life skills of senior high school students is never manifested.

The third tool is about the pedagogical endeavor. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Chronbach’s alpha value of 0.826. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made use the 5-Likert

scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers’ pedagogical endeavor, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the

schools division superintendant, and then to the school principals of the selected public secondary schools in the Tagum South District in the Division of Tagum City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last June 1-3, 2023. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey was briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration

Range of Mean, Description, and Interpretation

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ pedagogical endeavor is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ pedagogical endeavor is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ pedagogical endeavor is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ pedagogical endeavor is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ pedagogical endeavor is never manifested.

of the questionnaire, the researcher conducted the survey simultaneously. The respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of

Data. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondents was tallied to organized the data per indicator. After which, each score were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the engagement-based teaching approach, basic life skills, and pedagogical endeavor of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to asses the significant relationship among engagement-based teaching approach,

basic life skills, and pedagogical endeavor of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample it is usually denoted by *r*. Mediation Analysis Using JASP Software. It was applied to evaluate the mediating effect of pedagogical endeavor on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of students’ engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills; the significant relationship among the variables, and the mediating effect of pedagogical endeavor on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City.

The results in Table 1 reflects the summary on the extent of engagement-based teaching approach of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. The overall mean score on the engagement-based teaching approach of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City is 3.54 which was described as extensive. This implies that the pedagogical strategy in education that focuses on actively involving students in the learning process by promoting their participation, interaction, and interest in the subject matter is oftentimes observed. This supports the findings of Aninda (2018) that engagement-based teaching encourages students to think critically, ask questions, and solve problems. It fosters the development of analytical and problem-solving skills, which are essential in real-life situations.

Table 1. Summary on Engagement-Based Teaching Approach of Senior High School Students in Tagum South District, Tagum City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Teaching Engagement	3.73	Extensive
Interaction	3.44	Extensive
Feedback	3.43	Extensive
Overall	3.54	Extensive

As shown on the table, engagement-based teaching approach in terms of teaching engagement obtained the highest mean score of 3.73, while, engagement-based teaching approach in terms of feedback was rated with the lowest mean score of 3.43 which was described as moderately extensive. According to Kutbiddinova et al. (2016), engagement-based teaching actively involves students in the learning process, leading to deeper understanding and improved retention of the material. When students are engaged, they are more likely to master complex concepts and skills. Interactive and engaging lessons capture students' interest and motivation to learn. When students find the subject matter relevant and enjoyable, they are more likely to be intrinsically motivated to excel.

Overall, The results in Table 2 reflects the

As shown on the table, basic life skills in terms of critical thinking acquired the highest mean score of 3.80, while basic life skills in terms of decision making and problem solving

summary on the extent of basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. The overall mean score on the basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City is 3.45 which was described as extensive. This implies that the abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life is oftentimes manifested. This is congruent to Roodbari's et al. (2016) idea that life skills as an aptitude that combines knowledge, attitude, and skills in managing external problems in the current social situation as well as readiness for future self-adjustment in relation to sex, drugs, gender roles, family life, health, media influence, environment, ethics, and social problems.

skills was rated with the lowest mean score of 3.22 which was described as moderately extensive. According to Prasad (2018), interpersonal and psychosocial abilities help people make

Table 2. Summary on Basic Life Skills of Senior High School Students in Tagum South District, Tagum City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Critical Thinking	3.80	Extensive
Creative Thinking	3.55	Extensive
Self-awareness	3.45	Extensive
Interpersonal Relationship and Communication Skills	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Decision Making and Problem Solving Skills	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.45	Extensive

wise decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate clearly, form positive relationships, relate to others, and learn to manage their lives in a healthy and advantageous way. In essence, there are two categories of skills: thinking skills and social skills, which refer to abilities to interact with others.

Pedagogical Endeavor of Senior High School Students This variable as shown in Table 3 has a category mean of 3.60, described as extensive, which means that pedagogical endeavor is oftentimes manifested by the respon-

dents. This implies that the process of learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in teaching practice is oftentimes evident. This is similar to Jones and Dexter’s (2016) findings that high-level pedagogical endeavor involves tailoring instruction to individual students’ learning styles, abilities, and interests, fostering more effective and personalized learning.

Table 3. Pedagogical Endeavor of Senior High School Students in Tagum South District, Tagum City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Spending time and effort learning about and preserving the current information and skills, which are necessary for teaching practice.	3.56	Extensive
2. Determining my own learning needs by seriously reflecting on my teaching practices.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
3. Creating a professional development plan for my personal development.	3.78	Extensive
4. Looking for immediate responses to the questions emerging from teaching practice.	4.01	Extensive
5. Engaging actively in their pedagogic endeavor to foster effective education.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.60	Extensive

Adding on, the mean “Determining my own learning needs by seriously reflecting on my teaching practices” obtained a lowest mean rating of 3.29, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. The item, “Looking for immediate responses to the questions emerging from teaching practice” obtained the highest mean rating of 4.01 described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested by the respondents which are the senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. According to Kyrkjebø et al. (2017), educators experience professional growth, gaining a deeper understanding of effective teaching practices, classroom management, and student interaction. Likewise, Twining et al. (2013) noted that students benefit from engaging and effective teaching methods, leading to improved academic achievement and deeper understanding.

Relationship among Engagement-Based Teaching Approach, Basic Life Skills of Senior High School Students and Pedagogical Endeavor in Tagum South District, Tagum City

The results on the analysis on the relationship among engagement-based teaching ap-

proach, basic life skills of senior high school students, pedagogical endeavor are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned. Table 4 shows that engagement-based teaching approach has a significant positive relationship with basic life skills of senior high school students with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .441, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of engagement-based teaching approach changes, basic life skills of senior high school students also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students. This is congruent to Vinogradova’s et al. (2018) proposition that the introduction of interactive teaching methods is one of the most important areas for improving the training of students in a modern professional educational institution. Accordingly, the main methodological innovations are associated today with the use of interactive teaching methods.

Table 4. Relationship among Engagement-Based Teaching Approach, Basic Life Skills of Senior High School Students and Pedagogical Endeavor in Tagum South District, Tagum City

Variables	Basic Life Skills	Pedagogical Endeavor
Engagement-Based Teaching Approach	0.441**	0.244**
	0.000	0.000
Basic Life Skills	1	0.566**
		0.000

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r=1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 \leq r \leq 0.00$; No Correlation for $r=0.00$

On one hand, the result shows that engagement-based teaching approach and peda-

gogical endeavor has a significant positive relationship with a p-value of .000 that is less than

alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.244$ $p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of engagement-based teaching approach changes, the extent of pedagogical endeavor also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and pedagogical endeavor. The result supports the assertion of Goudreau et al. (2015) that teachers who demonstrate a strong commitment to pedagogical endeavor often become leaders in their schools, guiding and inspiring their colleagues. On the other hand, the result shows that the relationship between pedagogical endeavor and basic life skills of senior high school students with a p-value of .00 that is less than alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.566$ $p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of pedagogical endeavor changes, basic life skills of senior high school students also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between pedagogical endeavor and basic life skills of senior high school students. This is congruent to Millis' (2014) idea that effective pedagogical strategies manifest student-centered classroom management approach. In a student-centered learning environment the teacher gets to know her/his students, share their ideas and their management approaches allow them and their pupil to see one another as people.

Mediating Effect of Pedagogical Endeavor on the Relationship Between Engagement-Based Teaching Approach and Basic Life Skills of Senior High School Students in Tagum South District, Tagum City

Results on the Table 5 shows the mediating effect of pedagogical endeavor on the relationship engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City using Baron and Kenney's (1986) Method for Mediation. In this model, linear regression analysis was used to test the influence among variables. There are four steps to be met for a third

variable to be acting as a mediator. In Table 13, these are categorized as Path Coefficients (Steps 1 to 4). In Step 1, engagement-based teaching approach (EBTA) as the independent variable significantly predicts basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS) with is significant as indicated by estimate value of 0.466, $p < 0.05$, which is this study's dependent variable. In step 2, engagement-based teaching approach (EBTA) significantly predicts pedagogical endeavor (PE), the mediator, with estimate value of 0.361, $p < 0.05$. In step 3, pedagogical endeavor (PE) significantly predicts basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS) with estimate value of 0.476, $p < 0.05$. Because the three steps (paths a, b and c) are significant, further mediation analysis through medgraph is warranted, involving the Sobel z test to assess the significance of mediation effect. As gleaned in step 4 (parameter estimates), the effect of engagement-based teaching approach (EBTA) on basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS) was found to be significant after mediated by pedagogical endeavor (PE) with estimate value of 0.172, $p \leq 0.05$. Therefore, partial mediation took place since the effect was found to be significant at 0.05 level. Adding more, the total effect of engagement-based teaching approach (EBTA) as the independent variable on basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS), which is this study's dependent variable is significant, is significant as evident on the estimate value of 0.476 and $p < 0.05$. Also, it could be seen on the table that the direct effect of engagement-based teaching approach (EBTA) on basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS), is significant as indicated by estimate value of 0.466, $p \leq 0.05$. Lastly, the result of the computation of mediating effects is shown in the table. The Sobel z-test yielded a z-value of 3.312 with a p-value of 0.000, which is significant at 0.05 level. This means that the partial mediation accounted by pedagogical endeavor (PE) on the relationship between engagement-

based teaching approach (EBTA) on basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS) is significant. In addition, the table indicates the results of the computation of the effect size in the mediation test conducted between the three variables. As shown in the figure, the ratio index obtain a value of 0.2696 indicating that about 26.96 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes

through the mediator variable, and about 73.04 percent of the total effect is mediated by other variables not included in the model. Hence, the null hypothesis of pedagogical endeavor (PE) does not mediate the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach (EBTA) on basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS) is rejected.

Table 5. Mediating Effect of Pedagogical Endeavor on the Relationship Engagement-Based Teaching Approach and Basic Life Skills of Senior High School Students

Steps	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
(Step 1) EBTA → BLS	0.466	0.080	5.798	0.000
(Step 2) EBTA → PE	0.361	0.101	3.559	0.000
(Step 3) PE → BLS	0.476	0.054	8.764	0.000

Step 4 (Parameter Estimates)					
Effect Type	Parameter Estimates	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
Indirect Effect Components	EBTA → PE → BLS	0.172	0.052	3.297	0.000
Direct Effect	EBTA → BLS	0.466	0.080	5.798	0.000
Total Effect	EBTA → BLS	0.638	0.092	6.957	0.000
Ratio Index					0.2696
Sobel z-Test value					3.312, p<0.050

Legend: EBTA - Engagement-Based Teaching Approach, BLS - Basic Life Skills, & PE - Pedagogical Endeavor

The significant role of pedagogical endeavor as mediator in relationship between engagement-based teaching approach on basic life skills of senior high school students is contributed by the fact that there exist a relationship among these variables. It is emphasized in this study that pedagogical endeavor is an undeniable factor that explained relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students (BLS). This supports the idea of Cetin-Dindar (2016) that engagement-based teaching approach allows students to actively practice and apply basic life skills in various real-life scenarios. Whether it's through role-playing,

simulations, or hands-on activities, students get the chance to experience firsthand how these skills work in different situations. Lastly, the result corroborates with Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986) which highlighted the significance of observational learning, self-efficacy, reciprocal determinism, social reinforcement, cognitive mediation, and vicarious learning in the acquisition and development of these essential skills. The theory suggests that individuals can learn from the experiences of others. In interactive instruction, students may witness their peers demonstrating effective life skills, both through success and mistakes.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to determine the mediating effect of pedagogical endeavor of senior high school students on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using structural equation modelling through the use of mediation analysis. The researcher selected the 200 senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City as the respondents through random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Based on the results the summary of the findings were the following: Engagement-based teaching approach in Tagum South District in Tagum City has an overall mean of 3.54 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Also, engagement-based teaching approach in terms of teaching engagement, interaction, and feedback obtained the mean scores of 3.73, 3.44, and 3.43 respectively. Basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City has an overall mean of 3.45 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, basic life skills in terms of critical thinking, creative writing, self-awareness, interpersonal relationship and communication skills, and decision making and problem solving skills obtained the mean scores of 3.80, 3.55, 3.45, 3.26, and 3.22, respectively. More so, pedagogical endeavor in Tagum South District, Tagum City has an overall mean of 3.60 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Engagement-based teaching approach has a significant positive relationship with the basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .441, p < 0.05$). On one hand, engagement-based teaching approach has a significant positive relationship with the pedagogical endeavor with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .244, p < 0.05$). On the other hand, pedagogical endeavor has a significant positive relationship with the basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .566, p < 0.05$). Pedagogical endeavor mediate the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City. The analysis obtained the estimates value of 0.172 with $p < 0.05$, 0.466 with $p \leq 0.05$, and 0.638 with $p < 0.05$ for indirect, direct, and total effects, respectively. Moreover, the ratio index obtain a value of 0.2696 indicating that about 26.96 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 73.04 percent of the total effect is mediated by other variables not included in the model. The Sobel z-test yielded a z-value of 3.312 with a p-value of 0.000, which is significant at 0.05 level.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions are generated: Engagement-based teaching approach in Tagum South District in Tagum City

was described as extensive. On one hand, engagement-based teaching approach in terms of teaching engagement; interaction; and feedback belong to extensive rating. This implies that the pedagogical strategy in education that focuses on actively involving students in the learning process by promoting their participation, interaction, and interest in the subject matter is oftentimes observed. Basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City was described as extensive. On one hand, basic life skills in terms of critical thinking; creative writing; self-awareness; interpersonal relationship; and communication skills, and decision making and problem solving skills belong to extensive rating. This implies that the abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life is oftentimes manifested. Pedagogical endeavor in Tagum South District in Tagum City was described as extensive. This implies that the process of learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in teaching practice is oftentimes evident. Engagement-based teaching approach has positive significant relationship with basic life skills of senior high school students and pedagogical endeavor in Tagum South District in Tagum City. Also, pedagogical endeavor has positive significant relationship with basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District in Tagum City. Pedagogical endeavor mediate the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. This affirmed that pedagogical endeavor contributed significantly on the relationship between engagement-based teaching approach and basic life skills of senior high school students in Tagum South District, Tagum City. This means that engagement-based teaching approach al-

lows students to actively practice and apply basic life skills in various real-life scenarios.

4.3. Recommendations—The researcher recommends that the Department of Education should invest in comprehensive teacher training programs that equip educators with the skills to incorporate engagement-based teaching approaches and life skills development into their instruction. Adding more, DepEd should encourage and fund research initiatives that explore the effectiveness of engagement-based teaching approaches and the impact of life skills education on students' well-being and future success. The researcher recommends that school heads should ensure that the school's curriculum aligns with the development of life skills and promotes engagement in learning through interactive activities, projects, and real-world applications. In addition, they should create a positive and inclusive school environment that fosters student engagement, encourages the development of life skills, and values the well-being of both students and teachers. Teachers should incorporate diverse and interactive teaching strategies, such as active learning, group projects, and experiential learning, to engage students actively in the learning process. Adding more, teachers should integrate life skills development into subject-specific lessons and classroom activities, providing opportunities for students to apply these skills in real-life scenarios. Students should recognize the importance of life skills development and actively seek opportunities to apply these skills in daily life and future endeavors. Adding more, students should advocate for a well-rounded education that includes life skills training and engagement-based learning experiences, both within and beyond the classroom. Lastly, researchers should identify and explore research gaps in the areas of engagement-based teaching approaches, life skills development, and teacher pedagogical endeavors to contribute to the knowledge base.

5. References

- Achor, E. E., Danjuma, I. M., & Orji, A. (2019). Classroom interaction practices and students' learning outcomes in physics: Implication for teaching-skill development for physics teachers. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 3(6), 96–106. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1223015.pdf>
- Agbabi, C. O., Onyeike, V. C., & Wali, W. I. (2013). *Classroom management: A practical approach*. University of Port Harcourt press.
- Al-Bashir, M., Kabir, R., & Rahman, I. (2016). The value and effectiveness of feedback in improving students' learning and professionalizing teaching in higher education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(16), 38–41. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1105282.pdf>
- Alsafi, A. (2011). *Learning style preferences of saudi medical students* [Master thesis]. Essex University. <http://www.essex.ac.uk/linguistics/dissertations/2010/docs/Alsafi.pdf>
- Amin, M., Shah, R. U., Ayaz, M., & Atta, M. A. (2013). Teachers' job performance at secondary level in khyber pakhyunkhwa, pakistan. <http://www.gu.edu.pk/GUJR/PDF/Dec-2013/13Rahmat%20Ullah%20Shah.pdf>
- Aninda, R. P. (2018). *The use of interactive learning approach to improve the students writing descriptive text ability at the eighth grade of smp n 10 metro* [Master's thesis]. <https://repository.metrouniv.ac.id/id/eprint/1400/1/SKRIPSI%20RIZKY%20FIX.pdf>
- Aziz, Y., Safiah, S., & Zanariah, J. (2013). Critical thinking skills among final year students of malaysian technical universities. *Malaysian Technical Universities International Conference on Engineering & Technology (MUICET)*. <http://eprints2.utm.edu.my/3865/1/MUICET2011~AZIZYAHYA~PBPI.pdf>
- Baroody, A. E., Rimm-Kaufman, S. E., Larsen, R. A., Curby, T. W., & Abry, T. (2015). To what extent do teacher-student interaction quality and student gender contribute to fifth graders' engagement in mathematics learning? *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107(1), 170–185.
- Bierman, K. L., & Motamedi, M. (2015). Social and emotional learning programs for preschool children. In J. Durlak, C. Domitrovich, R. P. Weissberg, & T. Gullotta (Eds.), *The handbook of social and emotional learning: Research and practice* (pp. 135–150). Guilford.
- Buckley, P. (2015). Can the effectiveness of different forms of feedback be measured? retention and student preference for written and verbal feedback in level 4 bioscience students. *Journal of Biological Education*, 46(4), 242–246.
- Cenkseven Önder, F. (2015). The influence of decision-making styles on early adolescents' life satisfaction. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 40(9), 1523–1536.
- Con, M. K., & Cankaya, S. (2017). Problem-solving skills of futsal players with regard to some socio-demographic variables. *Turkish Journal of Sport and Exercise*, 19(2), 182–189. <https://doi.org/10.15314/tsed.313347>
- Demir, M. (2018). *Analysis on the relation between decision-making styles, personality traits, creativity and problem solving skills of football referees* [Doctoral dissertation, Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Physical Education and Sports, PhD Thesis, Kayseri: Erciyes University].

- Dhingra, R., & Chauhan, K. S. (2017). Assessment of life-skills of adolescents in relation to selected variables. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(8), 1–12. <http://www.ijsr.net>
- Elliott, V., Baird, J., Hopfenbeck, T., Ingram, J., Thompson, I., Usher, N., Zantout, M., Richardson, J., & Coleman, R. (2016). *A marked improvement? a review of evidence on written feedback* (tech. rep.). https://educationendowmentfoundation.org.uk/public/files/Publications/EEF_Marking_Review_April_2016.pdf
- Erawan, P. (2010). Developing life skills scale for high school students through mixed methods research. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 47(2), 169–186. http://www.ires.or.th/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/Life-skills-ejsr_47_2_02.pdf
- Eromasova, A. A. (2012). Intercultural interaction in the process of training of young specialists: Collective monograph. In V. Obukhov (Ed.), *Problems of education in the light of realistic philosophy* (pp. 122–123). Gamma.
- Esen, E. (2011). Employees organizational engagement. *Psychology*, 82, 184. <http://dosya.marmara.edu.tr/ikf/iib-dergi/2011-1/377-390esen.pdf>
- Fadhlullah, A., & Ahmad, N. (2018). Thinking outside of the box: Determining students' level of critical thinking skills in teaching and learning. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1207765.pdf>
- Friedrich, A., Flunger, B., Nagengast, B., Jonkmann, K., & Trautwein, U. (2015). Pygmalion effects in the classroom: Teacher expectancy effects on students' math achievement. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 41, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2014.10.006>
- Gee, J. (2013). Importance of prior knowledge to learning.
- Geisler, M., & Allwood, C. M. (2015). Competence and quality in real-life decision making. *PLoS One*, 10(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0142178>
- Greco, L. A., Baer, R. A., & Smith, G. T. (2013). Assessing mindfulness in children and adolescents: Development and validation of the child and adolescent mindfulness measure (camm). *Psychological Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0022819>
- Gülbahar, B. (2017). The relationship between work engagement and organizational trust: A study of elementary school teachers in turkey. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1127080.pdf>
- Hanum, N. S. (2018). The importance of classroom interaction in the teaching of reading in junior high school.
- Hargreaves, E., Gipps, C., & Pickering, A. (2016). Assessment for learning; formative approaches. In J. Arthur & T. Cremin (Eds.), *Learning to teach in the primary school* (3rd, pp. 313–324). Routledge.
- Heckman, J. J., Humphries, J. E., & Kautz, T. (2015). Fostering and measuring skills interventions that improve character and cognition. In *The myth of achievement tests* (pp. 341–430). <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226100128.003.0009>
- Jalaludin, M. A. B. M., & Ihkasan, M. N. B. (2016). Interpersonal communication skills among the master's students in tvet. *Developing Country Studies*, 4(16), 110–119. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234681881.pdf>
- Jalbani, L. N. (2014). *The impact of effective teaching strategies on the students' academic performance and learning outcome. a literature review* [Master's thesis]. <https://www.grin.com/document/300046>

- Jensen, M., Mattheis, A., & Johnson, B. (2015). Using student learning and development outcomes to evaluate a first-year undergraduate group video project. *CBE Life Sciences Education*, *11*(1), 68–80. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.11-06-0049>
- Jia, X. (2015). The application of classroom interaction in english lesson.
- Karataş, S., & Güleş, H. (2010). The relationship between primary school teachers' job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *Usak University Journal of Social Sciences*. <http://dergipark.ulakbim.gov.tr/usaksosbil/article/view/5000035925/0>
- Kashlev, S. S. (2013). Interactive methods of teaching pedagogy.
- Kawalekar, D. (J. S. (2017). The value of life skills in higher education. *IOSR Journal of Research Method in Education (IOSRJRME)*, *7*(3), 43–46. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-0703054346>
- Khanin, S. V. (2015). Using the case method as a method of interactive training in teaching the course "history of the internal affairs authorities". *Bulletin of the Nizhny Novgorod Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia*, *24*, 177–180.
- Kober, N. (2015). *Reaching students: What research says about effective instruction in undergraduate science and engineering*. <https://www.nap.edu/catalog/18687/reaching-students-what-research-says-about-effective-instruction-in-undergraduate>
- Kutbiddinova, R. A. (2015). Activation of educational activity of students through interactive methods. *Bulletin of the University*, *3*, 210–214.
- Kutbiddinova, R. A., Eromasovaa, A. A., & Romanovaa, M. A. (2016). The use of interactive methods in the educational process of the higher education institution. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, *11*(14), 6557–6572. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1115891.pdf>
- Leenknecht, M., & Prins, J. (2018). Formative peer assessment in primary school: The effects of involving pupils in setting assessment criteria on their appraisal and feedback style. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, *33*(1), 101–116.
- Leland, M. (2015). Mindfulness and student success. *Journal of Adult Education*, *44*(1), 19–24.
- Liu, Z. K., He, J., & Li, B. (2015). Critical and creative thinking as learning processes at top-ranking chinese middle schools: Possibilities and required improvements. *High Ability Studies*, *26*(1), 139–152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13598139.2015.1015501>
- Naseri, A., & Babakhani, N. (2016). The effect of life skills training on physical and verbal aggression male delinquent adolescents marginalized in karaj. *Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences*, *116*, 4875–4879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1041>
- Nivedita & B., S. (2016). Life skills education: Needs strategies. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, *3*(16), 3800–3806.
- Nonoyama-Tarumi, Y. (2017). Educational achievement of children from single-mother and single-father families: The case of japan. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, *79*(4), 915–931. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12409>
- Paul, R., & Elder, L. (2016). *Critical thinking: Tools for taking charge of your learning and your life*. Prentice Hall.
- Perez, L. M. (2014). Teaching emotional self-awareness through inquiry-based education. *Early Childhood Research & Practice*, *13*(2), 1–8.

- Prasad, J. (2018). Awareness of life skills among senior secondary school students of east and south districts of sikkim. <http://14.139.206.50:8080/jspui/bitstream/1/6077/1/jayashri%20prasad.pdf>
- Rani, R., & Menka, K. (2019). Life skills education: Concern for educationists for holistic development of adolescents. *Paripex - Indian Journal of Research*, 1(18), 31–32.
- Reeves, T. C. (2012). Interactive learning techniques. In N. M. Seel (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of the sciences of learning*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1428-6_331
- Reutova, E. A. (2015). The use of active and interactive training methods in the educational process of the higher education institution (methodical recommendations for the teachers of the novosibirsk state agrarian university), 58.
- Robson, S. (2016). The analysing children’s creative thinking framework: Development of an observation-led approach to identifying and analysing young children’s creative thinking. *British Educational Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3033>
- Roodbari, Z., Sahdipoor, E., & Ghale, S. (2016). The study of the effect of life skill training on social development, emotional and social compatibility among first-grade female high school in neka city. *Indian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Life Sciences*, 3(3), 382–390. <http://www.cibtech.org/jls.htm>
- Sidorenko, I. N. (2011). Use of interactive techniques in the teaching of social and humanitarian disciplines. *Proceedings of BSTU*, 8(146), 115–117.
- Singh, H. (2015). Strategies for development of life skills and global competencies. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 4(6), 2277–8179. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283491171>
- Son, H. V. (2018). Social awareness and responsible decision making of students in grade 4 and 5 in viet nam. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 4(7), 7–15.
- Sukhodolsky, D. G., Kassinove, H., & Gorman, B. S. (2017). Cognitive-behavioral therapy for anger in children and adolescents: A meta-analysis. 1789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2003.08.005>
- Vashishtha, K. (2015). Impact of life skills on leadership development. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management*, 2(3), 273–274. http://ijssm.org/vol_2/Vashishtha_2.3.pdf
- Vinogradova, M. V., Yakobyuk, L. I., & Zenina, N. V. (2018). Interactive teaching as an effective method of pedagogical interaction. <https://www.revistaespacios.com/a18v39n30/a18v39n30p25.pdf>
- Wang, M. (2017). The impact of teacher-student classroom interactions in primary school environment on children’s engagement in classroom: A systematic literature review. <http://www.diva-portal.se/smash/get/diva2:1106566/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Yildiz, N. G. (2015). Teacher and student behaviors in inclusive classrooms educational sciences. *Theory & Practice*, 15(1), 177–184.
- Zandvliet, D., Brok, P. d., Mainhard, T., & Tartwijk, J. V. (2014). *Interpersonal relationships in education: From theory to practice*. SensePublishers. https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/marietta/files/king_and_marietta_-_interpersonal_relationships.pdf